

MUJERES MARCHARAN

REPORT ON FEMICIDE AND
GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE
CRIMES IN TEXAS 2025

REPORT ON FEMICIDE AND GENDER BASED VIOLENCE CRIMES IN TEXAS, 2025

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INTRODUCTION

The UN Women has denominated femicides/feminicides the intentional killings of women and girls with gender-related motivations driven by stereotyped gender role myths, unequal power relations that discriminate against women and girls, and harmful social norms (UNODC & UN Women, 2022). Statistics from UN Women show that during the past decade, most of the intentional killings of women and girls in the world were gender-motivated, and 56% of these were committed by intimate partners or other family members (UNODC & UN Women, 2022).

In 1992, scholars and activists proposed the term femicide to name gender-based violence murders (GBV), highlighting its special nature as the product of discriminatory ideologies embedded in culture and social practices (Radford & Russell, 1992). Later, Marcela Lagarde (2005) translated the term to the Spanish *feminicidio* (feminicide), including in the concept the institutional discrimination experienced by the victims and their families during the criminal investigations by government officials in Mexico. GBV murders are a complex category; they represent the result of persistent actions of violence of a wide variety (Radford & Russell, 1992). The term femicide aims to encompass all misogynist murders in public and private contexts (Segato, 2014). Femicides can be committed by: (1) partners or ex-partners; (2) relatives (including dowry-related (Weil et al., 2016) and honour-related (Jiwani, 2014)); (3) friends or acquaintances taking advantage of the personal relationship with the victim; (4) community members to enforce codes and practices as in honour-related violence; (5) strangers and organized crime groups involving crimes that especially target women such as rape, trafficking, exploitation, hatred of women with stigmatized occupations (sex workers, escorts, dancers, waitresses), associated with torture, and public exhibition of the corpses (Berlanga Gayón, 2017; Monárrez Fragoso, 2009).

The word femicide/feminicide was created to make visible that these murders are hate crimes with a social dimension (Segato, 2014). The pervasiveness of extreme gender-based violence (GBV) is a consequence of discriminatory ideologies and practices embedded in society, perceived as natural common sense (Gopalan, 2022; Hunnicutt, 2009; Radford & Russell, 1992). False myths, such as the belief that women should be able to control their sexual behavior, but men cannot because of their natural impulses; the belief that men in the families are in control of women's bodies and lives; or the belief that men are more logical and make better decisions than women. These false beliefs are reproduced and perpetuated by influential

actors like politicians, the legal system, and the media (Segato, 2014; Wright, 2011). Hence, these discriminatory ideologies can influence the perceptions and attitudes of institutions and the community toward victims and perpetrators of gender-based violence crimes.

Despite the high prevalence of female murder victimization in the United States, the country lags behind other nations in defining and documenting gender-related female homicides, and deficient surveillance systems limit efforts to estimate the annual incidence of femicide (Lewis et al., 2024).

Following guidance from the UN Office on Drugs and Crime on a statistical framework for measuring femicide, registering sex/gender-related motives/indicators is necessary to ascertain whether the killing was a femicide. This is the first step for recognizing the severity of the problem and creating public efforts and policies to fight against this main social problem.

RECOUNTING FOR ACCOUNTABILITY PROJECT

Mujeres Marcharan, along with several non-governmental organizations, has recognized that counting and recording feminicides is a key practice to make it visible and strengthen evidence-based policy-making on this issue. Around the world, civil society actors are collecting and systematizing feminicides to challenge and change institutional data, which is often missing, messy, and lacks a socio-historical context on gender-based violence dynamics. The goal of these data activism practices is to understand better the what, when, where, how, and why regarding these killings, as there is a shared recognition that what or who is not counted does not count (Gatwiri et al., 2023).

Our main objective is to make visible the severity of the problem of femicide/feminicide and extreme gender violence in Texas, and especially in San Antonio. We built a database, valid and reliable, to show and prove the systemic and institutional violence embedded in our community. This tool serves the community to demand accountability from authorities, politicians, and news producers.

METHODOLOGY

Insofar as data on femicide/feminicide, news has been widely used as a source for producing datasets, especially in the absence of official data. In Mujeres Marcharan,

we partnered with experienced scholars and activists to train our data collection team in theoretical knowledge on femicide and gender-based violence, and data collection techniques. Several workshops were held to learn and discuss the collection processes, data, and coverage of specific cases.

The team agreed on which data should be registered and created a Google Form with these categories, open to the public, to register the news articles. Each article was read, and the person who registered it decided if the case fulfilled the criteria of informing a case of a gender-based violence crime committed in Texas. Femicide, as this category or concept is not used by news producers in Texas, the criteria we followed were: (1) it was an intentional murder or attempt, (2) the victim was a woman, (3) the perpetrator was a partner, ex-partner, or a family member, or (4) other circumstances suggest gender-related motivations. Difficult cases were discussed with other team members to decide if the article fulfills the criteria.

We found the news articles using two processes: web searching directly on the Texan news outlets by using keywords such as 'dead woman', 'murder of woman', 'rape', 'sexual assault', 'transwoman', and 'transman'. The second process is the tool 'Data Against Femicide Alerts' (https://alertas.datoscontrafemicidio.net/es/users/sign_in), which is available in English, Spanish, and Portuguese. This consists of an email alert platform created to facilitate the work of identifying news stories concerning femicide/feminicide cases. This tool uses a form of AI called machine learning to detect and compile news articles that are likely to refer to a case of femicide/feminicide and send an email to the data collection team members (Bhargava et al., 2022). The platform allows individuals and organizations to create their own project, choosing geographic limits, and specifying keywords used by local news makers.

Mujeres Marcharan, we created and tailored our project to the system to find gender-based violence crimes and femicides/feminicides, even when the news articles do not use these words. Each data collection team member registered in the platform as a user and was added as a collaborator for the project. We created a schedule for each team member to check the alerts on different weekdays to avoid double-registering the same article. All team members have access to read the Google Sheet that collects news articles, so they check if the article they register is

not already in the dataset. Just two members of the team can edit the Google Sheet that collects data to avoid mistaken data manipulation; one is the data supervisor. The supervisor is part of the data collection team, with the additional task of periodically reviewing the dataset to double-check that articles are not registered twice and to spot mistakes.

To ensure reliability, a copy of the Google Sheet was created, the dataset was divided, and four data collection team members reviewed one part to validate the data registered. The data was cleaned by deleting case duplicates.

The data collection is an ongoing process, but we cut on November 25, International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women. The findings presented in this report include statistics on crimes committed between January 1st and November 25th, 2025.

FINDINGS

FEMICIDE/FEMINICIDE

From January 1st to November 25th of 2025, 204 femicides were registered in Texas. Twenty-one of these occurred in San Antonio.

Considering the population in Texas is estimated at 31,853,800 inhabitants, of which 13.84 million are women, approximately 50.4% of the population.

The femicide/feminicide rate is **1.36 per 100,000 women**. If Texas were a country, it would be the 7th country with the highest rate of femicide in the world, after Honduras (4.3), Guatemala (1.9), Dominican Republic (1.5), Puerto Rico, Cuba, and Bolivia (1.4).

The situation in San Antonio is even worse, with a rate of **2.8 per 100,000 women**.

According to UN Women, 56% of the femicides/feminicides in the world are committed by a partner, ex-partner or a family member. Nonetheless, in Texas, 125 women were murdered in intimate partner or familiar femicides, which represent 62%.

This means that women and girls have an extremely high risk of being murdered by someone they trust and in their own home.

In San Antonio, only 3 women were intentionally killed by people they did not know.

Texas

San Antonio

*<https://www.cepal.org/es/comunicados/cepal-al-menos-19254-feminicidios-se-han-registrado-ultimos-cinco-anos-america-latina>

The highest risk is for women from 31 to 50 years old.

Femicide/feminicide Attempts

We found 47 cases of femicide/feminicide attempt, in 66% of these, the perpetrators were partners, ex-partners, or family members.

Fifteen of these crimes occurred in San Antonio.

Femicide/feminicide attempts differs from assaults because the perpetrator has the intention of fatally hurt the victims. This intention is presumed by the use of deadly weapons or because the murder was avoided by situation not in control of the perpetrator. Also can be indicated by the dead threats proffered by the perpetrator.

The victims' ages goes from 13 to 58 years old, which means that these women survivors will need family, community, and institutional support.

None of the news articles in our dataset used the word femicide or feminicide. Even when it is not a legal category in the United States, the wording could be helpful to generate awareness that these crimes are connected and part of a social system that allows extreme violence against women.

Hence, the murders are portrayed in the media as individual issues. Thirty-nine of these cases are denominated as murder-suicide, an old term that suggests personal problems.

Still, one of the main problems we found in the coverage is the lack of contextual information; just a few stories explain the previous history of intimate partner or family violence. This invisibilizes the fact that the murder is the final violent action suffered by these women and girls.

We also found that the articles do not bother to humanize the victims; 162 news stories identify the names of the victims, which is helpful to highlight that they are persons, not just corpses found dead. But rarely, the stories contain other descriptions that help to convey the human life that is lost.

Assault and Aggravated Assault

We registered 32 cases of assault or aggravated assault.
Eight in San Antonio.
The ages of the victims range from 6 to 35 years old.

Just two of these cases, the perpetrator was a stranger.

According to the law in Texas, assaulting a family member is an "aggravating factor" that increases the severity and punishment compared to a simple assault, even if the act itself is the same. Assault charges are a Class C misdemeanor, and against a family member are a Class A misdemeanor.

This means that the major risk for women and girls comes from partners and family.

Sexual Assault

We registered 123 cases of sexual assault, but 74 of these were against girls between 4 and 17 years old, representing 60% of the cases.

22 cases in San Antonio.

As statistics across regions show, our data evidence that women and girls are most likely to be sexually abused by someone they know or a member of their own family.

Sexual Assault by Victim-Perpetrator Relationship

Prostitution

We found at least 13 cases of prostitution. Two of them were charged with sexual exploitation of children, and at least one case of a 17-year-old girl.

Legal frame in Texas.

Solicitation: State jail felony for a first offense, with penalties potentially increasing for repeat offenses or if the person involved is a minor.

Engaging in prostitution: Class B misdemeanor for first-time offenders, carrying a potential jail sentence of up to 180 days and/or a fine of up to \$2,000.

Promoting prostitution, known as pimping or pandering, is also a crime.

Aggravated penalties: A second or third offense of soliciting prostitution can be a third-degree felony. If the person solicited is under 18, the charge can be a second-degree felony.

Nonetheless, the legal framework disregards contextual situations, as in the cases where women are exploited, physically, and mentally abused. Which impede them from accusing their perpetrator, and many times, women end up charged with prostitution.

Kidnapped or Missing

We found an alarming number of kidnapped or missing girls and women.

Ninety-three cases in Texas, ten in San Antonio.

Especially girls between 15 and 17 years old.

Other Gender-Based Violence Crimes

We also found:

- Two Vicary Murders (Boyfriend murdered girlfriend's son)
- One Transfemicide
- One case of discrimination against a Trans Woman
- Three Homophobic Murders (Two in San Antonio)
- Five cases of Stalking, Harassment, and Sexual Harassment

It must be noted that these crimes may be under-reported in the news, as many times they do not comply with the journalistic values to publish them.

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